

The Role of Reserve Components in Supporting Indonesia's Defense Forces to Face Non-Military Threats

Vincentius A.M.Kusuma¹, Zainal A.Sahabuddin², Posma S.J.K. Hutasoit³ Muhtar Rifai⁴

¹(Student in Defense Economics Department, Republic of Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

²(Lecturer in Economics Department, Republic of Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

³(Lecturer in Economics Department, Republic of Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

⁴(Student in Defense Economics Department, Republic of Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

Abstract: Facing the Threats of the State Indonesia will strengthen defense from non-military elements (multidimensional) in the future. Indonesia's defense paradigm should change, relying solely on the TNI as its mainstay. The dramatic decline in (traditional) military threats from other countries, as well as similar threats around the world, rethink the optimal formula for Indonesia's defense strategy in the era of non-military threats. For this reason, it is necessary to consider the formation of reserves. Previously, he had good skills and knowledge about State Defense. defense, these reservists can work as a defensive element to support the main force, especially when facing non-military threats. The deployment of reserve troops is not only ready for war, but also has the main function of assisting the TNI with Threats, Distractions, Obstacles and Challenges (AGHT) because the current war is not an intangible fire. This paper describes how reservists as part of Defense will be exposed to non-military threats in the future. In addition, this paper also sees that defense can be an integral part of the reservist's efforts to achieve this.

Keywords: Reserve Components, National Defense, Defense, Non-Military

I. INTRODUCTION

The existence of a country in the life of the state is part of the defense. In the era of globalization, the forms of threats are increasingly complex. Threats, disturbances, obstacles, and challenges (AGHT) that must be answered by this country no longer come from outside (external). AGHT originating from the outside changed its form from purely military (conventional) to non-military (non-conventional). Not only transboundary phenomena such as terrorism, drugs, human trafficking, environmental destruction, population growth, food, and energy scarcity, economy, corruption, politics, refugees, identity crises, natural disasters, but also national problems.

The current political constellation of the world aligns war with the nature of proxy wars. War is quasi (pseudo), so those with a strategic interest in war do not participate directly or remain unknown. Understanding this distinctive threat requires a different approach. The Indonesian National Armed Forces (TNI) and the National Police certainly find it difficult to deal with all existing restrictions. For this reason, the formation of Komcad as a component of a non-military defense force that supports the main defense unit (TNI) is very important. The supporting component is a non-military AGHT solution. The establishment of a backup component can help support the main component especially due to the limitations of the main component and the potential for emergencies (unforeseen circumstances).

Sukzaya in his book Dharmawan said that the power of state defense or the strength of state defense is the determination, attitude, and action of citizens in an orderly, comprehensive, integrated, and sustainable

manner based on their love for the homeland and their perceptions of the state and state life. State defense has always been the right, obligation, and responsibility of all parts of the state. In other words, defending the country is the duty and responsibility of its citizens to maintain its existence and sovereignty. Protecting the country is not only the duty and responsibility of the TNI but the responsibility of all of us.

The characteristics of future conflicts, the nature of national and international threats, and Indonesia's national interests conceptually encourage the formation of a defense strategy that is in line with the dynamics of the times. The combination of the components of state defense and reserves must be able to fight for the national interest in the defense sector. The originally physical war (hard power) became a diplomatic war (soft power). Non-conventional threats also refer to the term human security. Phenomena that are the subject of discussion of non-conventional threats include terrorism, drugs, human trafficking, environmental destruction, politics, ideology, separatism, and natural disasters. The many non-military threats facing this country in this global era must be faced through several policies that play an effective role in their respective fields.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. *Defense Science*

Strategor 'Military Science' or 'Military Science' or 'Art of Science of War', also called war science and contemporary Defense Science. There are two main figures in the science and art of war in the world, namely Sun Tzu and Carl von Clausewitz. In the period before Christ, Sun Tzu worked on "The Art of War" which included discussing "war" which was widely used in actual war applications. Even today, Sun Tzu's knowledge of the "Art of War" has been transformed and implemented into various fields, especially in business management. Sun Tzu questions issues related to morality, leadership, cunning, and tactical innovation (Supriyanto, 2014). Sun Tzu defines war on a grand strategic level, with more consideration for diplomatic and economic factors (Halkis, 2020).

General Carl von Clausewitz in his book entitled "On War" which was written two centuries ago provides a fundamental view for the military and civilians. For civilians, discussing what is considered when going to war, for example, war is a continuation of politics, problems of economic power, statistical factors, geometric factors, strategy, elements of strategy, moral factors, military values. From the military side, Clausewitz discussed issues at the policy, strategic and operational levels, as well as tactics on the battlefield. This means that fighting is a decision, defense, and attack, security (Supriyanto, 2014). Clausewitz assumes that the factors have been considered and the analysis begins in the strategic-operational realm, essentially where war will soon occur (Halkis, 2020).

Defense science is an applied science, namely how to use and mobilize the national power of a nation and state to deal with threats. The approach used is to utilize science related to defense.

2.2. *Reserve Components*

The reserve component is a non-military defense element, generally formed and prepared to use the potential of national resources, such as citizens, to become a defense force that can be used to improve and strengthen the TNI. Even though this is its basic function, namely to deal with military threats, under certain conditions, especially current conditions, reserve components can be used to deal with the increasing number of non-military threats. Multiple non-military threats These include the involvement of reserve components in humanitarian operations, handling natural disasters, cyber threats, border security, countering terrorism, and separatism (Soepandji in Sukadis and Hendra, 2008).

Meanwhile, according to Article 1 paragraph 6 of the state defense law, reserve components are national resources that have been prepared to be deployed through mobilization to enlarge and strengthen the strengths and capabilities of the main components. More clearly, the reserve component is defined as the

mobilization of the people to physically defend the state, where some of them are trained in military basics to a certain extent so that they are ready to be mobilized if the state needs it when a threat comes.

2.3. Non-Military Threat

Non-military threats in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2002 concerning Defense are called non-military threats, which are a form of threat that uses non-military factors which are considered to be harmful to sovereignty, territorial integrity, and the safety of the entire nation and state. Non-military threats can come from abroad or can come from within the country. Non-military threats are classified into several dimensions such as ideology, politics, economy, socio-culture, technology, public safety, and legislation at the local, regional, and national levels (www.kemhan.go.id).

This security is called securitization. These issues can involve the military in their handling efforts, such as fighting drug crimes, assisting humanitarian operations, to combating terrorism. Military and non-military domains also influence each other. That's why, for example, the issue of terrorism, in which there is a problem of radicalization, we can classify as a non-conventional issue because it has undergone a process of securitization (Indrawan, 2015). Defense issues are also currently being mixed with security, especially related to unconventional threats. That is, the battlefield is starting to widen, ranging from physical war (hard power) to invisible (soft power) (Samego, 2015).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Method study used is descriptive with a qualitative approach. The survey method used is a qualitative method. Qualitative research aims to preserve the form and content of human behavior and analyze its nature rather than converting it into quantitative units (Mulyana, 2008). The purpose of this descriptive research is to make a systematic and factual explanation, picture or painting about the facts, characteristics, and relationships between the phenomena studied. The data collection method used by the researcher is observation, interviews, and documentation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Currently, the national defense requires a reserve component, Indonesia is building a defense based on a universal people's defense system, or a system that utilizes all national resources to overcome its threats. In this system, defense is not only the responsibility of a particular agency (TNI or Ministry of Defence) but also the responsibility of all parts of the country as regulated in Articles 1 and 2 of the 1945 Constitution. Including all national resources for national defense, it is necessary to regulate law based on democracy, respect for human rights, and civil hegemony.

The use of resources is clearly defined by the National Defense Act. However, so far, there has been no legal regulatory system in the form of political decisions (laws). Indeed, in an emergency, the state will need the available resources to support its interests. Therefore, it is necessary to form special laws and regulations that regulate national resources to support the strength of the TNI. In this regard, the Ministry of Defense has ratified the National Resource Management Act (UU PSDN) since 2013 as the legal umbrella for state democracy in using national resources for defense. The PSDN Law is a simplification of the National Defense Forces Bill, the Reserve Troops Bill, the Supporting Troops Bill, and troop mobilization.

This research is only focused on how to reserve components that are part of a country's defense resources can become a competent defense force in the face of non-military threats that are increasingly common today. Because this is a combination with the National Defense Bill, adequate knowledge and skills are needed to protect the country if the reserve forces are later formed by the PSDN Law. The National Defense Force is a mandatory curriculum that must be taught in the early stages of basic military training in the reserve.

Based on the PSDN Law, particularly in Article 12, basic military training is mandatory for citizens in the form of providing basic military skills for future reserves.

The national defense force according to the Defense Law is universal, includes the entire civilian population, territory, and other resources, and is prepared in advance by the government. The resources referred to are human resources, natural resources and production, value, technology, and finance that can be used to strengthen the defense capability of a country. The defense system faces two threats as well as military threats and non-military threats. For this reason, the TNI as a key component of defense needs to be supported by two additional components, namely a reserve component and a supporting component.

The reserve component is a national resource based on Article 1, Paragraph 6 of the National Defense Law and is deployed to develop and enhance the strength and capability of the key components. More specifically, reserve forces are defined as the mobilization of the population for the physical defense of the state, and those who have a certain level of military training to prepare the country for mobilization in the event of a threat. The Reserve Force is a non-military defense element that is commonly formed and is ready to utilize the potential of national resources such as civilians to become a defense force that can be used to improve and strengthen the TNI. Even if this is its basic function, defense against military threats is, of course, especially in the current circumstances, Army reserve components can be used to counter increasing non-military threats. Several non-military threats, such as the participation of reservists in this humanitarian activity, natural disasters, cyber threats, border security, anti-terrorism, and eradication of separatism.

Law Number 34 of 2004 concerning the Indonesian National Army, Article 7 Military Operations Other Than War (OMSP), stipulates that reserve forces can also be involved in OMSP as part of improving the implementation of the Universal Defense System (Sishanta). According to the understanding of the universal defense system, universal war is defined as including civilian (non-military) elements to support the armed forces known as reserves. For this reason, the authors believe that the level of non-military threats is increasing and backup components need to be configured.

Reserve Components (Komcad) represent an existential potential to assist the defense in the face of non-military threats. The reserve forces are not the main force like the TNI, but they have a civilian character. The use of this component is certainly more effective in the nature of non-military threats that do not use weapons but are more ideological, political, economic, social, cultural, or religious. If action is needed, the TNI or Polri will step in and respond. The reserve component is not an element of military defense, but a non-military element. Philosophically, reserve forces are generally formed to be able to use the potential of national resources (humans, artificial objects, natural resources, national facilities, and infrastructure, etc.) as elements of the Defense Force in strengthening the main components of the TNI. Reserve troops benefit the state as part of a national security program by providing troops at a lower cost than the state must pool to fund active (regular) troops. Reserve troops are ready to be deployed or assigned to repair and enhance the functions of the TNI.

Threats of obstacles and challenges (AGHT) that Indonesia is currently facing are political problems (idealism, freedom, elections, regional autonomy), economic problems (limited state budget, high fuel, and food prices), and community problems (disasters including law enforcement). national law). level or public order and decency and security (smuggling of goods, terrorism, conflicts between denominations). At the regional level, there are border conflicts, maritime security, and transboundary crimes. Indonesia's challenges and threats at the international level are human rights issues, foreign intervention, the war on terror, regional or international conflicts, and weapons of mass destruction.

This situation reinforces the fact that military or invasion of Indonesia from other countries is not possible now or in the future. Estimates in the Indonesian Defense White Paper (2015). For this reason, reserve forces can be the best choice for predicting the worst non-military threat scenario and the worst military threat if it occurs one day. Therefore, countries preparing for defense must do more than just military preparations, as mentioned above, in addition to military threats. For example, to overcome non-military threats that constantly attack the state ideology, Pancasila, the public needs to understand Pancasila in a pure and consistent manner.

That way, these people can be given the opportunity to become educators, such as for state defense training related to the practice of Pancasila. Such people can definitely be included in the reserve component.

Likewise, for example, the threat of terrorism. So far, counterterrorism has only focused on the minimal level of law enforcement and prevention, despite implementing radicalization policies. One of the efforts to prevent intensification that leads to terrorism is cyber prevention. In Indonesia, many cyber experts are needed to fend off the negative effects of people who want to spread malicious expressions, hoaxes, and radical content. These cyber experts should be part of the backup component.

Based on the examples of non-military threats above, we can see that Indonesia's current and clear threats are non-physical threats. This type of threat cannot be tackled by military responders alone. However, countering this type of threat requires a different approach. As already explained, reserves are not part of the military defense force. For that, the commitment must also be right. This means that we need to deal with non-military threats that are currently increasing, evolving and undefined. Therefore, an important reserve component was immediately formed to counter the doctrines in the frame of non-military threats.

The rationale for establishing a reserve component is to view defense as a national effort to maximize national potential and resources for the benefit of defense. The doctrine of defense (SISHANKAMRATA) allows the state to implement it. In some countries, reserves take different forms and roles, called reservists or conscripts, and are tailored to the needs of the country.

In European countries, military service programs are implemented in many countries such as France, Finland, Russia, and Germany. Historically, the term conscription was first introduced during the French Revolution of 1789. At that time, all French citizens were soldiers. In its development, the French conscript army was able to defeat the special army of the European monarchy. Since the 18th century, many European countries have introduced conscription programs. Especially during the Cold War, when almost all Eastern European countries served their citizens. However, after the Cold War, when the world's strategic environment changed, many countries began to abandon conscription facilities.

There are at least three design models in Europe. First, there are suspended drafts or drafts made in the event of a threat or emergency such as a crisis or war. This military service can also be applied to foreigners such as the French (French Foreign Legion) and Spain. Belgium and Luxembourg, on the other hand, were the first European countries to accept EU citizens as part of their military service. Second, general military service, i.e. military service for all citizens. If a citizen cannot comply, he must pay compensation. This program also applies to women. However, due to global developments in European regulations prohibiting forced labor, many countries have abandoned policies to employ women for military service. Countries with conscription are Switzerland, Austria, Greece, and Finland. Third, the symbolic or elected military service is used in some Scandinavian countries. Denmark is an example of a military service system that invites young people to volunteer in the military. However, if a certain recruitment quota is not reached, the government will use a lottery to determine which citizens need to participate in military service. This system is also known as complementary military service and is practiced in Sweden, Norway, and Germany. the government will use a lottery to determine which citizens need to participate in military service. This system is also known as complementary military service and is practiced in Sweden, Norway, and Germany. the government will use a lottery to determine which citizens need to participate in military service. This system is also known as complementary military service and is practiced in Sweden, Norway, and Germany.

In the United States, the situation depends on the situation and the government. During the Civil War of 1863, all Americans had to serve in the military. This rule continued during World War I and World War II, and the Vietnam War in the 1960s. Since 1973, the government has only required citizens to enlist voluntarily and without obligation and discontinued the general military service policy (also known as the selective service system, teams). Since the end of the Cold War, the United States has faced no significant threat, so the policy of conscription will not be strictly enforced during this time of peace.

However, the Selective Service System program will continue to function and will have no legal consequences for those who do not comply. Then, after the terrorist attacks of 11 September 2001, Afghanistan had to prepare a large number of troops in preparation for the invasion, and many troops were deployed to fight Afghanistan and Iraq. In Australia, in addition to the regular army, the Australian Government uses reserve forces to solve civilian electricity and water-related problems. Since the use of reservists is governed by the organizational structure of the national armed forces, approval of reservists varies in practice and is in the interest of individual countries.

Indonesian reservists need not take such an example to learn from the draft case above. Indonesia should adopt a registration model like the United States. In the United States, reserve forces are still formed without obeying civilians. The people who follow him have two main roles. That is, the nation's fighting ability in the event of a military threat and actions according to their respective professions to deal with these non-military threats. Reserve troops are mobilized only when the country is threatened militarily. Otherwise, after mandatory basic military training, the reservists will return to their respective professions. They will participate in efforts to overcome non-military threats that become the competitive arena of this sector.

Therefore, the author has the thought that reservists are required by Indonesian law as part of the Indonesian Defense, especially for non-military AGHT. Overcoming the challenges of the strategic environment in this era of globalization really requires good reserve power and good reserve power. An era marked by the development of science, technology, communication, and information. Defense can be an integral part as taught at the beginning of the basic military reserve training. Facing non-physical threats that are invisible to the eye, all members of the reserve forces need an idealistic foundation, national spirit, and strong nationalism. This was the essence of the ability to protect the condition of every reservist. Because they study all things philosophical, not everything physical. It doesn't make sense to have good fighting skills, but that doesn't mean you don't have the spirit of Pancasila. It doesn't make sense to have high intelligence, but the low spirit of nationalism.

The purpose of defending the state is to defend the nation and its survival, maintain its culture, carry out the values of Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution, do the best for the nation and its people, as well as for identity in supporting the nation and state which includes perfection. Therefore, the state defense movement is expected to foster the following attitudes. (1) Forming a disciplined attitude towards time, activities, and other activities. (2) The formation of a spirit of unity and unity among fellow activists. (3) Take strong mental and physical form. (4) Instilling a sense of love and love for the homeland to the community according to their abilities. (4) Develop leadership both by yourself and in groups. (5) The formation of faith and devotion to the religion of each individual. (6) Be filial to parents, state, and religion. (7) Train speed, dexterity, and accuracy in carrying out activities. (8) Eliminate negative attitudes such as laziness, indifference, extravagance, egoism, and lack of discipline. (9) Above all, establish honest, strong, fair, accurate, and loving behavior.

V. CONCLUSION

National defense is the attitude and actions of citizens inspired by the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia which guarantees the survival of the country and the existence of the dedication of the State ready to sacrifice for the country. Reserve Components are non-military defense elements that are usually formed and prepared to utilize the potential of national resources such as military vehicles. Reserve components can represent an existential potential to assist defense in the face of non-military threats. The reserve forces are not the main force like the TNI, but they have a civilian character. The use of this component is certainly more effective in the nature of non-military threats that do not use weapons but are more ideological, political, economic, social, cultural or religious.

State Defense Material is a mandatory curriculum that must be taught in the early stages of basic military training in the reserve army. Defending the country's citizens is the right and obligation to protect and protect the independence and sovereignty of the nation, territorial integrity, and the security of the nation as a whole from all threats. Defense achieved through participation in defense efforts is the responsibility and honor

of all citizens. Therefore, citizens are obliged to participate in national defense, including participation in the reserve forces. Reserve troops are required by Indonesian law as part of the Indonesian Defense, especially for non-military AGHT. To answer the challenges of the strategic environment in this era of globalization, a good reserve army and main force are urgently needed. These are usually of domestic (internal) origin and are insignificant.

With a typical threat like the one above, it is impossible to hand over to the TNI, let alone the police. In Law Number 34 of 2004 concerning the Indonesian Armed Forces (TNI), Article 7 concerning Military Operations Other than War (OMSP), stipulates that in the framework of organizing the Universal People's Defense and Security System (Sishankamrata) reserve components can also be involved in OMSP. In Sishankamrata's understanding, universal war is defined by the inclusion of civilian (non-military) elements involved in military support, called reserves. For this reason, reserves as a non-military defense element can be formed as the main reserve force.

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